

Net Zero Evaluation Metrics for Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI)

Authors: Charlotte Pascoe, Molly MacRae

What does “good” look like?

Traditional metrics to assess the prowess of high performance compute (HPC) and high throughput compute (HTC) facilities generally describe the speed and capacity of a facility. The pathway to net zero will require new climate metrics that also cover the energy use and efficiency of a facility and the emissions embodied in the supply chain of the equipment within it.

A key recommendation from the Net Zero DRI scoping project is the need to create standards for recording and reporting energy usage and efficiency¹. The standards should incorporate all three GHG Protocol emission scopes. The metrics will need to be developed in conjunction with appropriate tools and hardware/software specifications so that they are accessible to all system and facility managers.

The development of new climate metrics will allow procurement benchmarks² for DRI services to be evaluated using energy efficiency metrics as well as traditional performance metrics. For these metrics to be effective, the procurement processes must be adapted to empower institutions making purchases to include climate metrics in their decisions³, to balance investments in energy efficiency against investments in energy intensive infrastructure, and to convert efficiency gains into carbon savings⁴.

Accelerator hardware (microprocessors that are capable of accelerating certain workloads such as GPUs (Graphical Processing Units) and FPGAs (Field Programmable Gate Arrays)) have been proved to reduce the energy-to-solution of some HPC workloads⁵. Whereas other types of code have benefited from a reduction in CPU frequency⁶. Correct decisions require good information, therefore benchmarking efforts and associated training and development are needed to improve our understanding of how to optimise computing environments for energy efficiency for different classes of algorithms.

¹ Ag Stephens, Gabin Kayumbi, & Simon Lambert. (2023). Report on the DRI Mapping Survey 2023 (UKRI Net Zero DRI Scoping Project) (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7805988>

² Turner, Andrew, & Basden, Alastair. (2022). HPC-JEEP: Energy Usage on ARCHER2 and the DiRAC COSMA HPC services (v1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7137390>

³ Manika, Danae, McCarroll, Niall, Buck, Justin, Lopez, Alvaro Lorenzo, Geatches, Dawn, Ahrens, Florian, Krumdieck, Susan, Keshtkar, Hossein, Fayyad, Nadine, & Hassanloo, Hamidreza. (2023). Giving Voice to, and Empowering Stakeholders of UKRI DRI: A Net Zero Workshop Series (Go Zero). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7692290>

⁴ Juckles, Martin, Pascoe, Charlotte, Woodward, Lucy, Vanderbauwhede, Wim, & Weiland, Michele. (2022). Interim Report: Complexity, Challenges and Opportunities for Carbon Neutral Digital Research. Zenodo. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7016952

⁵ Bane, Michael K., Brown, Oliver, Bhowmik, Deepayan, Quinn, Jamie, Ali, Teymoor, Quinn, Jamie, & Stansby, David. (2023). ENERGETIC: Final Report. Zenodo. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7692272

⁶ Smith, Lorna, Simpson, Alan, Moran, Laura, & Turner, Andy. (2023). ARCHER2 Net Zero Case Study. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7788498>

Technology changes which reduce energy consumption in use can also increase the supply chain energy demand (e.g. the shift from spinning disks to solid state storage in personal computers). When evaluating the carbon footprint of a piece of Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI) equipment, embodied emissions are a key consideration and can make up a substantial part of the total emissions. To understand overall emissions, vendors should be required to provide high quality information on the carbon impact of the manufacturing and delivery of hardware⁶.

Standardised metrics that cover both emissions from in use energy consumption and embodied emissions will be key to balancing competing factors and finding a path that minimises the climate impact of DRI.

Supporting Recommendations

A general discussion of the recommendations can be found in section 3.2 of the [Net Zero DRI Scoping Project's final technical report: Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure](#)⁷. A full list of the recommendations can be found in Appendix 3 of the final report and in addition can be accessed via this [spreadsheet](#).

Recommendation 7: Avoid the rebound effect at the procurement stage. Ensure procurement framework enables the conversion of efficiency gains into carbon savings rather than simply resulting in higher usage.

Recommendation 12: Procurement that balances investment in energy efficiency against investment in infrastructure.

Recommendation 35: Invest in accelerators according to energy savings. ... The accelerators should include GPU and FPGA technologies and further benchmarking efforts to improve understanding of differences in energy efficiency across different classes of algorithms.

Recommendation 43: Procurement process. Current procurement process leaves little room to account for energy efficiency in hardware and software.

Recommendation 58: Procurement benchmarks. Procurement benchmarks for HPC services should be evaluated on energy efficiency metrics as well as traditional performance metrics.

Recommendation 75: For future procurements, vendors should be required to provide high quality information on the carbon impact of the manufacturing and delivery of the hardware.

Recommendation 81: Some, but not all, codes may benefit from a reduction in CPU frequency. Correct decisions require good information (e.g., instrumentation).

Recommendation 104: Create standards for recording and reporting energy usage and efficiency. Agree standard metrics for recording and sharing efficiency and energy usage information.

⁷ Juckes, M., Bane, M., Bulpett, J., Cartmell, K., MacFarlane, M., MacRae, M., Owen, A., Pascoe, C., & Townsend, P. (2023). Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure: UKRI Net Zero DRI Scoping Project final technical report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199984>